

Syntheses and structures of two tetracopper(II) complexes with 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,3-benzenedicarboxaldehyde bis(benzohydrazone)[†]

Swamy Maloth and Samudranil Pal*

School of Chemistry, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad-500 046, India

E-mail : spal@uohyd.ac.in

Abstract : The reaction of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,3-benzenedicarboxaldehyde bis(benzohydrazone) (H_3L) in methanol affords a tetranuclear complex of formula $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{L})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2]$ (**1**). On the other hand, the reaction of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_3L in presence of KOH in methanol affords **1** as minor product and a second solvated tetranuclear complex $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) as the major product. Both complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic, infrared spectroscopic and X-ray crystallographic measurements. The asymmetric unit of each complex contains a dinuclear unit which dimerizes and forms the tetranuclear complex. The two metal centres in the dinuclear unit are bridged through an endogenous phenolate-O and an exogenous methanolate-O. In **1**, the dinuclear unit $\{\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})(\text{OCH}_3)\}$ dimerizes through two pairs of weak reciprocal equatorial-apical bridges involving one iminolate-O of L^{3-} and the methanolate-O atoms, while the dinuclear unit $\{\text{Cu}_2(\text{HL})(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\}^+$ of **2** dimerizes through a similar pair of weak reciprocal equatorial-apical bridges involving only the methanolate-O atom. In these tetranuclear structures, each metal centre is in square-pyramidal NO_4 coordination sphere. In the crystal lattice, a one-dimensional ordering of **1** occurs due to intermolecular π - π interactions, whereas $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ forms a three-dimensional framework via intermolecular N-H \cdots O, O-H \cdots O, O-H \cdots N hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions.

Keywords : Tetranuclear copper(II) complexes, dialdehyde bis(benzohydrazone), syntheses, crystal structures.

Introduction

Dinuclear copper(II) complexes are of considerable interest primarily with respect to structural and functional mimicking of various metalloenzymes and magneto-structural correlations¹. Acid hydrazides and acid hydrazide based Schiff bases belong to an important class of ligands that provides diverse types of transition metal complexes having interesting structural and physicochemical properties. Such ligands and their complexes are also well known for their biological activities and potential applications as pharmaceuticals and functional materials². We have been working on complexes of copper(II) with a variety of acid hydrazide based Schiff bases for the past several years³. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-1,3-benzenedicarboxaldehyde bis(benzohydrazone) (H_3L), derived from one mole equivalent of the dicarboxaldehyde and two mole equivalents of benzohydrazone is one of the Robson type pentadentate dinucleating N_2O_3 donor Schiff base.

Using H_3L , we attempted the synthesis of a dinuclear copper(II) complex of empirical formula $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})(\text{OR})]$ and examine the effect of protonation state of the ligand amide functionality on its structure and properties. In this effort, we isolated two tetracopper(II) complexes namely $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{L})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**2**) which are essentially the dimers of the originally attempted dinuclear core⁴. Herein, we describe the syntheses, characterization and single crystal X-ray structures of these two tetranuclear complexes.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Experimental

Materials :

The Schiff base (H_3L) was prepared in good yield (82%) by reacting benzohydrazide and 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,3-benzenedicarboxaldehyde in 2 : 1 mole ratio in methanol by following a procedure very similar to that reported in literature⁵. All other chemicals and solvents used in this work were of reagent grade available commercially and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental (C, H, N) analyses were performed using a Thermo Finnigan Flash EA1112 series elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured with a Sherwood Scientific balance. Diamagnetic corrections calculated from Pascal's constants⁶ were used to obtain the molar paramagnetic susceptibilities. Infrared spectra were recorded by using KBr pellets on a Jasco-5300 FT-IR spectrophotometer. X-Ray powder diffraction patterns were collected on a Philips PW-3710 diffractometer using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$).

Syntheses of complexes :

$[Cu_4(L)_2(OCH_3)_2]$ (**1**) : A methanol solution (10 mL) of $Cu(O_2CCH_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$ (50 mg, 0.25 mmol) was added to a methanol (15 mL) suspension of H_3L (50 mg, 0.125 mmol). Immediately the reaction mixture turned into green and it was refluxed for 3 h. After cooling to room temperature the solution was allowed to evaporate slowly. The complex separated as green crystalline material was collected by filtration, washed with little ice-cold methanol and finally dried in air. The yield was 46 mg (66%). Anal. Calcd. for $Cu_4C_{48}H_{40}N_8O_8$: C, 51.89; H, 3.63; N, 10.08. Found : C, 51.76; H, 3.68; N, 10.15%; $\mu_{eff}/\text{per Cu}$ (300 K) : 1.34 μ_B .

$[Cu_4(HL)_2(OCH_3)_2(H_2O)_2](ClO_4)_2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ (**2**) : A methanol solution (15 mL) of $Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (93 mg, 0.25 mmol) was added to a methanol solution (15 mL) of H_3L (50 mg, 0.125 mmol) and KOH (14 mg, 0.25 mmol). The mixture was heated to reflux for 3 h. After cooling to room temperature complex **1** obtained as precipitate (25 mg, 36%) was filtered and the green filtrate was allowed to evaporate slowly.

After 2–3 days $2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ separated as a crystalline material was collected by filtration, washed with ice cold methanol and finally dried in air. The yield was 40 mg (44%). Anal. Calcd. for $Cu_4C_{50}H_{58}N_8O_{22}Cl_2$: C, 41.47; H, 4.04; N, 7.74. Found : C, 41.36; H, 4.48; N, 7.75%; $\mu_{eff}/\text{per Cu}$ (300 K) : 1.44 μ_B .

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of both **1** and $2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ were collected directly from the corresponding synthesis reaction mixtures. The unit cell parameters and the intensity data for **1** were obtained on a Bruker-Nonius SMART APEX CCD single crystal diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 298 K. The SMART software was used for data acquisition and the SAINT-Plus software was used for data extraction⁷. An absorption correction was performed with the help of SADABS program⁸. An Oxford Diffraction Xcalibur Gemini single crystal X-ray diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromator and a Mo $K\alpha$ fine-focus sealed tube ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) was used for unit cell determination and intensity data collection of $2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ at 298 K. The CrysAlispro software⁹ was used for data collection, reduction and absorption correction. Both complexes crystallize in the triclinic $P\bar{1}$ space group. Each of the two structures was solved by direct methods and refined on F^2 by full-matrix least-squares procedures. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms of the water molecules (coordinated and lattice), methanol-OH and protonated amide N-H of $2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ were located in a difference map and except for the N-H proton the remaining were refined with geometric and thermal (1.5 times that of the atoms to which they are attached) restraints. The N-H proton was refined isotropically. All other hydrogen atoms of $2 \cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ and all the hydrogen atoms of **1** were included in the structure factor calculations at idealized positions by using a riding model. The SHELX-97¹⁰ programs available in the WinGx¹¹ suite were used for structure solution and refinement. The Mercury¹² and the Platon¹³ packages were used for molecular graphics. Selected crystallographic data are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Selected crystallographic data

Complex	1	2 ·2CH ₃ OH·2H ₂ O
Chemical formula	Cu ₄ C ₄₈ H ₄₀ N ₈ O ₈	Cu ₄ C ₅₀ H ₅₈ N ₈ O ₂₂ Cl ₂
Formula weight	1111.04	1448.10
Crystal system	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> $\bar{1}$	<i>P</i> $\bar{1}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	8.3167(17)	8.3910(17)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.3072(19)	12.101(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.745(3)	15.059(3)
α (°)	79.53(3)	88.27(3)
β (°)	80.95(3)	86.40(3)
γ (°)	81.84(3)	74.44(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1100.8(4)	1470.0(5)
<i>Z</i>	1	1
ρ (g cm ³)	1.676	1.636
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.973	1.603
Reflections collected	10642	9767
Reflections unique	3859	5157
Reflections (<i>I</i> ≥ 2σ(<i>I</i>))	2997	4220
Parameters	309	410
R1, wR2 (<i>I</i> ≥ 2σ(<i>I</i>))	0.0377, 0.0930	0.0400, 0.1075
R1, wR2 (all data)	0.0517, 0.0989	0.0512, 0.1110
GOF (<i>F</i> ²)	1.039	1.067
Max./Min. Δρ (eÅ ⁻³)	0.442, -0.252	1.023, -0.583

Results and discussion

Syntheses and characterization :

The complexes [Cu₄(L)₂(OCH₃)₂] (**1**) and [Cu₄(HL)₂(OCH₃)₂(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ (**2**) have been synthesized in moderate to good yields by reacting one mole equivalent of dinucleating pentadentate N₂O₃ donor Schiff base H₃L (2-hydroxy-5-methyl benzene-1,3-dicarbaldehyde bis(benzoylhydrazone)) with two mole equivalents of Cu(O₂CCH₃)₂·H₂O (for **1**) and Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in presence of KOH (for **2**) in methanol. Complex **1** was isolated as it is without any solvent molecule, while complex **2** was obtained as 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O. It may be noted that some amount of **1** is also formed during the synthesis of 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O. The elemental analysis data are in good agreement with the molecular formulas of **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O. The effective magnetic moments (per Cu) of **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O at room temperature (300 K) are 1.34 and 1.44 μ_B, respectively. These values are lower than the spin-only value (1.73 μ_B) of copper(II) (*S* = 1/2). Thus in each complex an antiferromagnetic interaction is operative between the metal ions.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of H₃L and complexes **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O were collected in KBr disks. The free Schiff base H₃L shows the phenolic-OH and the amide-NH stretching (ν_{OH} and ν_{NH}) bands at ~3432 and ~3214 cm⁻¹, respectively. Two overlapping strong bands observed at 1651 and 1626 cm⁻¹ have been attributed to the amide C=O and the azomethine C=N stretching (ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=N}) bands, respectively. Absence of any band related to the phenolic OH and the amide (-C(=O)NH-) functionalities of the free Schiff base (H₃L) in the spectrum of **1** indicates complete deprotonation and trianionic state (L³⁻) of the ligand in the complex. Three medium to weak broad bands observed at ~3580, ~3520 and ~3355 cm⁻¹ for 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O are very likely due to the OH groups of the coordinated and lattice solvent molecules¹⁴. A broad relatively weak band at ~3200 cm⁻¹ and a sharp medium intensity band at 1622 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the O-coordinated protonated amide functionality^{14,15} of the ligand (HL)²⁻ in **2**. A medium intensity sharp band observed at 1614 and 1603 cm⁻¹ for **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O, respectively is assigned to the azomethine moieties of the corresponding ligands. A very strong and broad band centred at ~1100 cm⁻¹ and a sharp and strong band at 623 cm⁻¹ observed for 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O are typical of its counter anion perchlorate.

Description of X-ray structures :

The structures of both **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O were determined by single crystal X-ray structural analyses. The structures of **1** and **2** are illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. In the dinuclear unit of each structure, the pentadentate dinucleating ligand forms 5,6,6,5-membered fused chelate rings and the metal centres are bridged by an endogenous phenolate-O and an exogenous methanolate-O. Bond parameters associated with the metal centres for **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O are listed in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Bond lengths in both complexes are comparable with the corresponding bond lengths reported for copper(II) complexes having similar coordinating atoms^{3,5,15a,16}.

The asymmetric unit of **1** contains a single dinuclear unit {Cu₂(L)(OCH₃)} where metal centres are in square-planar N₂O₂ geometries (Fig. 1). In this dinuclear unit, both the amide functionalities of the pentadentate N₂O₃

Fig. 1. ORTEP (50% probability ellipsoids) of the asymmetric unit (top) and the perspective view (bottom) of the tetranuclear structure of **1**.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Cu1-O1	1.933(2)	Cu2-O3	1.891(2)
Cu1-N2	1.895(3)	Cu2-N3	1.904(3)
Cu1-O2	1.938(2)	Cu2-O2	1.908(2)
Cu1-O4	1.925(2)	Cu2-O4	1.929(2)
Cu1-O4 ^a	2.455(2)	Cu2-O1 ^a	2.692(2)
O1-Cu1-N2	82.68(10)	O3-Cu2-N3	82.45(10)
O1-Cu1-O2	174.16(8)	O3-Cu2-O2	173.40(9)
O1-Cu1-O4	105.61(9)	O3-Cu2-O4	104.04(9)
O1-Cu1-O4 ^a	89.18(9)	O3-Cu2-O1 ^a	90.10(9)
N2-Cu1-O2	91.57(10)	N3-Cu2-O2	92.81(10)
N2-Cu1-O4	169.51(10)	N3-Cu2-O4	173.44(9)
N2-Cu1-O4 ^a	102.62(10)	N3-Cu2-O1 ^a	98.53(10)
O2-Cu1-O4	79.99(9)	O2-Cu2-O4	80.64(9)
O2-Cu1-O4 ^a	93.09(9)	O2-Cu2-O1 ^a	95.17(9)
O4-Cu1-O4 ^a	84.19(9)	O4-Cu2-O1 ^a	82.59(9)

Symmetry transformation used to generate equivalent atoms : $a-x+1, -y+1, -z+2$.

Fig. 2. ORTEP (50% probability ellipsoids) of the asymmetric unit (top) and the perspective view (bottom) of the tetranuclear complex dication (bottom) of **2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O**.

Table 3. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for **2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O**

Cu1-O1	1.944(2)	Cu2-O3	1.923(3)
Cu1-N2	1.935(3)	Cu2-N3	1.911(3)
Cu1-O2	1.927(2)	Cu2-O2	1.933(2)
Cu1-O4	1.944(2)	Cu2-O4	1.949(2)
Cu1-O5	2.276(3)	Cu2-O4 ^a	2.355(3)
O1-Cu1-N2	82.31(11)	O3-Cu2-N3	82.57(11)
O1-Cu1-O2	170.73(10)	O3-Cu2-O2	170.94(10)
O1-Cu1-O4	104.35(10)	O3-Cu2-O4	104.11(10)
O1-Cu1-O5	94.14(10)	O3-Cu2-O4 ^a	94.15(10)
N2-Cu1-O2	91.04(11)	N3-Cu2-O2	91.89(11)
N2-Cu1-O4	164.87(11)	N3-Cu2-O4	169.24(11)
N2-Cu1-O5	96.79(11)	N3-Cu2-O4 ^a	104.51(11)
O2-Cu1-O4	80.64(10)	O2-Cu2-O4	80.37(10)
O2-Cu1-O5	93.06(10)	O2-Cu2-O4 ^a	94.18(10)
O4-Cu1-O5	96.27(10)	O4-Cu2-O4 ^a	83.64(10)

Symmetry transformation used to generate equivalent atoms : $a-x+1, -y+1, -z+1$.

donor ligand (L^{3-}) are deprotonated. This $\{Cu_2(L)(OCH_3)\}$ unit dimerizes through two pairs of weak reciprocal equatorial-apical interactions involving the iminolate-O and the methanolate-O atoms and the discrete centrosymmetric tetranuclear species $[Cu_4(L)_2(OCH_3)_2]$ (**1**) is formed (Fig. 1). This tetranuclear structure has a face fused double pseudo-cubane (two opposite corners are missing) $\{Cu_4(\mu_3-O)_2(\mu_2-O)_4\}$ core (Fig. 3). Due to this dimerization, each metal centre becomes five-coordinated. The geometry index τ values (0 for ideal square-pyramid and 1 for ideal trigonal bipyramid)¹⁷ are 0.08 and 0.00 at Cu1 and Cu2, respectively and hence the metal centres are in essentially ideal square-pyramidal NO_4 geometry. The equatorial bond lengths are in the range 1.891(2)–1.938(2) Å, while the weak apical Cu-O(iminolate) and Cu-O(methanolate) bond lengths are 2.692(2) and 2.455(2) Å, respectively (Table 2). The intra-tetranuclear metal-metal distances span a large range. The Cu1-Cu2, Cu1-Cu1^a, Cu1-Cu2^a, and Cu2-Cu2^a distances are 2.9379(12), 3.2695(11), 3.3189(12) and 5.3482(19) Å, respectively.

It may be noted that quite some time ago, before we isolated and structurally characterized **1**⁴, the X-ray struc-

Fig. 3. The $\{Cu_4O_6\}$ cores in **1** (left) and **2** (right).

ture of the dimethylformamide (dmf) solvate of its dinuclear unit was reported^{5a}. Interestingly, in this case, the solvated $\{Cu_2(L)(OCH_3)\}$ unit does not dimerize. The shortest Cu-O(apical) distance in $[Cu_2(L)(OCH_3)] \cdot dmf$ was found to be 3.645(5) Å. However, the same tetranuclear structure of **1** synthesized by using a different method compared to ours has been reported very recently^{5c}.

The asymmetric unit of **2** $\cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$ contains one cationic dinuclear unit $\{Cu_2(HL)(OCH_3)(H_2O)\}^+$, one perchlorate, one water molecule and one methanol molecule (Fig. 2). In the asymmetric unit there are three hydrogen bonds (Table 4). These are between the metal coordinated water O-H and the perchlorate-O, the amide N-H and the lattice water-O and the lattice water O-H and the methanol-O. The cationic dinuclear unit of **2** is similar to that of **1** except for the two dissimilar amide functionalities of the pentadentate N_2O_3 -donor ligand (HL^{2-}) with respect to their protonation states and coordination of the extra water molecule at the apical site of the square-pyramidal Cu1 (Cu1-O5 = 2.276(3) Å and $\tau = 0.1$). The comparison of the C7-N1 (1.346(5) Å) and C7-O1 (1.257(4) Å) bond lengths with the C16-N4 (1.325(5) Å) and C16-O3 (1.296(4) Å) bond lengths clearly indicate that N1 is protonated while N4 is deprotonated. The difference in the protonation state of the amide functionalities is also reflected in the longer Cu1-O1(amide) (1.944(2) Å) and shorter Cu2-O3 (iminolate) (1.923(3) Å) bond lengths (Table 3). As in **1**, here also the dinuclear cation dimerizes to form the centrosymmetric tetranuclear dication of **2** but in a slightly different fashion (Fig. 2). The dimerization occurs via a pair of weak reciprocal equatorial-apical bridges involving the methanolate-O atom (O4) and

Table 4. Hydrogen bonds in **2** $\cdot 2CH_3OH \cdot 2H_2O$

$\angle D-H \cdots A$ (°)	$d(D \cdots H)$ (Å)	$d(H \cdots A)$ (Å)	$d(D \cdots A)$ (Å)	$\angle D-H \cdots A$ (°)
N(1)-H(1A) \cdots O(11)	0.75(5)	2.03(5)	2.755(4)	163(5)
O(5)-H(5A) \cdots O(9)	0.96(1)	1.964(14)	2.906(4)	167(3)
O(11)-H(11A) \cdots O(10)	0.99(1)	2.04(4)	2.715(5)	124(4)
O(5)-H(5B) \cdots N(4) ^a	0.96(1)	1.875(14)	2.811(4)	165(3)
O(10)-H(10A) \cdots O(6) ^b	0.98(1)	1.868(17)	2.815(6)	162(3)
O(11)-H(11B) \cdots O(8) ^c	0.97(1)	1.965(14)	2.920(5)	170(4)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms :

^a-x+2, -y+1, -z+1. ^b-x+2, -y+1, -z. ^cx, y-1, z.

the square planar metal centre (Cu2) (Cu2-O(methanolate) = 2.355(3) Å). As a result, all the metal centres including Cu2 ($\tau = 0.03$) in the tetranuclear $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ resides in square-pyramidal NO_4 coordination environment. The dimerization and the resulting structure is very similar to that of **1** except for the non-participation of the iminolate-O atom in dimerization ($\text{Cu1}\cdots\text{O3}^a = 2.902(3)$ Å). Thus the $\{\text{Cu}_4(\mu_3\text{-O})_2(\mu_2\text{-O})_2\text{O}_2\}$ core of this tetranuclear dication may be best described as face fused double pseudo-cubane (two opposite corners and two opposite edges are missing) (Fig. 3). Due to the similarities of the $\{\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_6\}$ core structures, the metal-metal distances in the tetranuclear dication are very similar to the corresponding distances in **1**. The Cu1-Cu2, Cu2-Cu2^a, Cu1-Cu2^a and Cu1-Cu1^a distances are 2.9468(9), 3.2192(10), 3.3515(12) and 5.4285(17) Å, respectively.

Self-assembly :

Both structures have been examined for intermolecular non-covalent interactions and the ensuing self-assembled supramolecular structures. Complex **1** assembles to a one-dimensional chain-like structure^{5c} via intermolecular π - π interactions between the C1-C6 and the C17-C22 rings (dihedral angle = 10.6° and Cg \cdots Cg distance = 4.218(2) Å). No significant hydrogen bonding interaction could be detected in this case. However, as expected, several intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions involving the dicationic tetranuclear complex, the solvent (methanol and water) molecules and the perchlorate anion are operative in the crystal lattice of $2\cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Table 4). The trapped solvent molecules and the perchlorate play important roles in shaping the final supramolecular structure. The solvent molecules and the perchlorate form a six-membered $\{(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)\}_2^{2-}$ ring with the help of O-H \cdots O interactions. Each dicationic complex is connected to four of these six-membered molecular rings via two O-H \cdots O (coordinated water O-H and perchlorate-O) and two N-H \cdots O (amide N-H and water-O) interactions. This combination of one complex dication and four molecular rings may be considered as the primary motif. Similarly, in the secondary motif, each six-membered molecular ring is connected to four dicationic complexes through the same two O-H \cdots O and two N-H \cdots O interactions (Fig. 4). These two motifs lead to a two-dimensional sheet-like arrangement of the methanolated hydrated complex (Fig. 5). The bare complex dications form a one-

Fig. 4. Primary (top) and secondary (bottom) motifs via hydrogen bonding in $2\cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 5. Two-dimensional assembly of $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ ions and the six-membered $\{(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)\}_2^{2-}$ rings (top) and O-H \cdots N assisted chain-like structure of $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ having inter-chain π - π interactions on both sides (bottom).

Fig. 6. Three-dimensional framework of $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ viewed along a -axis (left) and c -axis (right).

dimensional chain-like structure via the O-H \cdots N (coordinated water O-H and amidate-N) interactions. Each of these one-dimensional chains are connected to the adjacent chains through π - π interactions involving the C1-C6 ring (dihedral angle = 0° , Cg \cdots Cg distance = 3.720(3) Å and inter-planar distance = 3.395 Å). Thus the bare complex dications assemble to another two-dimensional sheet structure through the O-H \cdots N and the π - π interactions in the ac -plane and this second sheet structure is orthogonal to the first sheet structure formed by it together with the six-membered $\{(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})(\text{ClO}_4)\}_2^{2-}$ rings. As a result of these two mutually orthogonal sheet structures a three-dimensional framework of $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is assembled (Fig. 6).

Powder X-ray diffraction studies :

The phase purity and homogeneity of the bulk **1** and $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were confirmed by comparing their experimental powder X-ray diffraction patterns with the patterns simulated from the corresponding single crystal data. The experimental and simulated diffraction patterns are very similar for **1**, whereas for $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ they are somewhat different (Fig. 7). This difference is attributed to the loss of the lattice solvent molecules (methanol and water) during grinding of the sample.

Fig. 7. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of **1** ((a) experimental and (b) simulated) and $2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ((c) experimental and (d) simulated).

Conclusion

The dinucleating Schiff base 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,3-benzenedicarboxaldehyde bis(benzohydrazone) (H_3L) provides two tetranuclear complexes of molecular formulas $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{L})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{HL})_2(\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ -

(ClO₄)₂·2CH₃OH·2H₂O (2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O) in moderate to good yields. Both complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, infrared spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis. The crystal structures reveal that in each complex the dicopper(II) unit formed by the N₂O₃-donor dinucleating Schiff base ligand and the ancillary bridging methanolate ligand dimerizes to a centrosymmetric tetranuclear species having a face fused double pseudo-cubane {Cu₄O₆} core. Each metal centre in these tetranuclear complexes is in square-pyramidal NO₄ coordination environment. Scrutiny of the self-assembly patterns via intermolecular non-covalent interactions reveals a π-π interaction assisted one-dimensional ordering of **1**, while 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O assembles to a three-dimensional framework through N-H···O, O-H···O, O-H···N hydrogen bonding and π-π interactions.

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Supplementary data

CCDC 1437102 and 1437103 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for **1** and 2·2CH₃OH·2H₂O, respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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